

IDEAS AND OBJECTIONS TOWARDS BEING A PERFECT HUMAN BEING IN RELATIVE WORKS ON EDUCATION OF YOUTHS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7428073>

Annotation: In this article, the image of a perfect person, which occupies a special place in the works of *Makhtumquli*, which everyone wants to see, the origin of perfection, the requirements for a person who has achieved perfection, the qualities of perfection, what achievements a person can achieve to be perfect, perfection in the personality of Makhtumquli thoughts about it will be highlighted.

Key words: Perfection, education, *Makhtumkuli*, pedagogy, *Alisher Navoi*.

Today, peace, tranquility and prosperity reign in our heavenly country. The value of these blessings is priceless. This peace, development and prosperity certainly did not happen by itself. First of all, this is the infinite grace of Allah Almighty, and secondly, it is the result of the rational policy of our government. However, in the current era, one thing should be emphasized, that in all times, it has been very important to educate young people to be knowledgeable and to improve their manners and morals. For this purpose, along with the care provided by our state, the constant efforts of parents, enlightened elders, neighborhood activists, school administrators and imam-khatibs are very important. Therefore, it is necessary to inculcate the views of our great scholars on education and the meaning and content of their works into the minds of young people, to educate them in the spirit of a perfect person, a well-rounded person, which is necessary for the well-being of our society today.

First of all, let's find an answer to the question of who is the perfect person. Al-Insan al-Kamil (*Arabic* - in Sufism, the vicegerent of Allah on earth and the ideal person who manifests his attributes and names. This term was introduced by *Hallaj*, and the idea was developed by *Ibn Arabi*. In a broad sense - a "religious person" who has achieved high spiritual maturity through religious practice comes in the meaning.

The education of a perfect person has always been considered an important social task, and a well-educated person was considered a wealth of the society. A person's beauty is measured by the knowledge he acquires. If educated people are considered mature in the teachings of Islam, we can see that in the views of our thinkers, it is necessary to acquire many characteristics in order to be a perfect person.

In the literary heritage of Makhtumkuli, the word "*perfection*" has been developed, which is distinguished mainly by knowledge, profession, and good behavior. First of all, Allah Almighty gives the first lessons of perfection in any sphere of living and working as a pure person in social life, profession and craft. Makhtumquli considers it his sacred duty to perfect human language and poetry in an energetic, emotional, impressive, instructive and educational way. "He tries to find and destroy the dragon that hides in everyone's mind. Although one person out of a thousand is a person, and the rest are just shadows, the poet wants to find a perfect human quality in every student, and he does not give up on the search for it.

The concept of a perfect person has a deep meaning. The concepts of thinking, life and social culture combine to form a whole. The past, present, and future of every nation originates from this culture. "*It would be a sign of ignorance to ignore, or to fail to appreciate, this comprehensive understanding*"¹.

The poet's philosophy about the age of perfection is in harmony with the people's philosophy. The issue of perfection in the literary legacy of the wise child of all times, the faithful and wise child of all times, who devoted all his mental strength, ability, and creative perfection to raising human dignity, is an urgent issue. These include a number of important issues: master-disciple perfection, state building perfection, speech perfection, manners perfection, knowledge perfection, professional perfection, love perfection, human relations perfection, interstate relations perfection. It is clear that Makhtumkuli set himself the goal of developing the general culture of the people through his works. Studying a person is the basis of a poet's work." In his poems, the wise poet Makhtumkuli talks openly with the reader about his scientific and practical views and life lessons on the topics of "heart, soul, heart, inner world, inner world, inner desire, character, life lessons". Such poems, in fact, are born from the great poet's deep connection with the feelings of the Turkmen people, as a manifestation of his inner nature. Initially, 314 poems of Makhtumkuli were translated by Jumaniyaz Sharipov. Originally published as Selected Works in 1958, these translations were republished in slightly abridged form in 1960, 1963, and 1976.²

¹ Oraz Yag'mur. Makhtumkulinoma. - T.: —UZBEKISTON; NMIU, 2016. –p.5.

² Makhtumkuli. Selected works. - Tashkent.: Science, 1958.;

Makhtumkuli. Selected works. - Tashkent.: Literary publishing house of Uzbekistan, 1960;

Makhtumkuli. Selected works. - Tashkent.: 1963;

From the poetry of Makhtumkuli. - Tashkent.: Publishing House of the Central Committee of Uzbekistan, 1976.

If we think based on the quatrains written by Makhtumquli, we can see that his views on the perfect man were inspired by Alisher Navoi, who he considered one of his absent teachers. It is not an exaggeration to say that views on the Perfect Man were one of the main ideas in the works of many of our scholars in all times, because the desire to be a perfect person in their hearts never left them throughout their lives, always striving for it and hoping for it. Lived for this reason, the scholars of the East who lived and created before Makhtumkuli also expressed the following thoughts about the perfect human being.

Abu Nasr Farabi says that a person cannot reach perfection alone. He will need contact with others, their support or relationships. This can be achieved through proper education. Because education carried out in accordance with the purpose makes a person mature both intellectually and morally. As a result, a person learns the laws of nature and society correctly, follows the right path in life, and has good relations with others. It emphasizes the fact that the formation of a perfect person is a single whole, integrated two directions

Abu Raykhan Beruni considers the foundation of perfection to be knowledge and emphasizes that the main cause of all evils is ignorance. According to Alloma, morality, correctness, justice, entrepreneurship, self-restraint, modesty, honesty, prudence, as well as being fair and conscientious are the most basic qualities that should be reflected in the image of a perfect person. *Abu Ali ibn Sina* also mentions being educated as the main criterion for reaching maturity. Evaluating that the justice of a knowledgeable person ensures his further advancement, he points out that justice is an important indicator of mental peace. He considers the formation of moral characteristics in a child in a harmonious unity with work, physical and mental education, the main factor in making him a real human being.

In the works of *Alisher Navoi*, the problem of the perfect person occupies a central place, and he tries to embody the mature person of his dreams in the form of the heroes of his works. He emphasizes that a perfect person should be intelligent, moral, knowledgeable, creative, capable, wise, humble, humanitarian, generous, patient, just, kind, healthy, physically strong, brave and brave. Having to overcome some difficulties in learning shows that it is possible to have perfect knowledge only by being resilient, contented, and enduring along the way.

Inspired by these teachers, Makhtumquli was able to enter the hearts of the people as a leader who was able to follow the people in his time. Makhtumquli's ideas about the perfection of the teacher act as a spiritual school and guide us in every aspect of the social structure, that is, in the issue of state management.

Every day of Makhtumkuli will make your heart flutter. "Everyone discovers the secret of Makhtumkuli in his own way. Every time you read it, new secrets are revealed. Every time, the reader immerses himself in the ocean of thought and enjoys the pleasures of meaning.

In this matter, he follows the path of his predecessors, but looks further than them³. There is no limit to the amount of time you can live to be perfect. The teaching of the School of Perfection is a lifelong companion of a person. The wise poet happily sat down and talked face to face. He advises, sighs, or meditates on good deeds, or artistically describes the state of mind, the reality of life. He finds comfort in the conversation with him. This conversation is the heartbeat of a genius poet. This conversation is the voice of the heart of the entire Turkmen people. This is a poetic expression of the voice that arises in the heart of every Turkmen. This is a vivid proof of the poet's ability to use artistic creativity at an artistic level. This is a unique school of poetry, which further connected its fate with the art of poetry, the story of writers, the approach of scientists to the use of words in science, and the literary school that left them a legacy.

The ideas put forward in the works of the wise poet serving as a school of humanity, the words of the ancestors, which are the national philosophy of the Turkmen people, are presented in harmony with the ideas of the proverbs. Both Makhtumquli and matal proverbs reveal the inner feelings of a person with wonderful purposes. For example, the poet bequeathed to God the blessings given to man and the perfection of using the word, which is the fruit of man, for strange purposes and says, *"The spoken word is the pattern of the heart..."*. Proverbs and proverbs about perfection and perfection:

Donoligim do'stim, nodoligim dushmanim.

(Wisdom is my friend, ignorance is my enemy.)

G'azab - aqlning dushmani, ochko'zlik - iymon.

(Anger is the enemy of reason, greed is faith.)

Qalam tutgan qo'l qashshoqlikni bilmaydi.

(The hand that holds the pen knows no poverty.)

Keksalikdagi sevgi suyakni sindiradi.

(Love in old age breaks the bone.)

Har bir insonning aqli mukammal ko'rinadi.

(Everyone's mind seems perfect.)

ilm-fan yonib turgan chiroq.

(science is a burning lamp.)

³³ Oraz Yag'mur. Makhtumkulinoma. - T.: —UZBEKISTON; NMIU, 2016. —p.5.

Mohir yigit xor bo'lmas,

(A skilled young man is not to be despised.)

Do'st-dushman kerakmas.

(Friends and enemies are not needed.)

Ikki kengash bir bo'lsa, ellik yigit yuz bo'ladi.

(If two councils are one, then fifty young men will be one hundred.)

Mening bilimim yaxshi - men yaxshiman.

(My knowledge is good - I am good.)

Birinchidan - ish, keyin - ovqat.

(First - work, then - food.)

Ish hikmat topadi, donolik ish topadi.

(Work finds wisdom, wisdom finds work.)

In short, Makhtumkuli is a real high example for contemporary poets and for the common people who lived with him at that time. It would be appropriate to recognize Makhtumquli as a "*poet of the human soul*" and "*a poet beyond human incarnation, one lifetime, one era.*" Makhtumquli teaches his people important lessons about good and bad, honesty and dishonesty, beauty and ugliness, wisdom and carelessness. If you read Makhtumquli when you are happy, the poem will double your happiness, if you are sad, it will comfort you, and if you are angry, it will calm your heart. Thus, the qualities of Makhtumkuli, such as patriotism, honesty, and love for visual arts, became an example for many generations. Nothing compares to his love and warmth for his native people. During his entire life, he was able to find his place in the hearts of people as a passionate, philanthropic person who worked only for his people to achieve perfection, give them spiritual food, and lead a prosperous life.

References:

1. Oraz Yagmur. Makhtumkulinoma. - T.: –UZBEKISTON; NMIU, 2016. –p.5.
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